

RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING WITH POWDER-COATED PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

Incomplete fiber wetting in a resin transfer molded composite part may result in poor surface finish, high void content, and reduced mechanical properties. This work studied whether or not the use of tows that are pre-coated with a powdered version of the liquid molding resin (towpregs) to make preforms improves the final part properties due to better fiber wetting. Hercules 12K AS-4 fibers and PR500 (liquid) and PS500 (powder) resins (3M) were used to make fabrics from towpregs containing 50% by weight total resin (liquid and powder combined). The powder weight fractions were 0, 13, 21, 50%. Samples were resin transfer molded from preforms made from the towpreg fabrics. Results showed that samples molded with powder-coated preforms had improved surface finishes and reduced void contents (1.43 vs. 5%), but that the mechanical properties were not improved (transverse moduli of approximately 7.8 GPa and axial moduli of approximately 100 GPa), probably due to defects inherent in the hand-woven towpreg fabric used in the experiments.

KEYWORDS: resin transfer molding, preforms, powder fusion coated towpreg

1. INTRODUCTION

An important aspect of the resin transfer molding process is fiber wetting. If the fibers are poorly wet-out by the matrix, voids will occur and poor fiber-matrix bonding will occur. These will lead to reduced mechanical properties and lower quality surface finishes. Resin flow through a fibrous preform can be broken down into two types: macroscopic and microscopic. [1,2] When considering a preform consisting of woven or aligned fiber bundles, macroscopic flow is the flow through the preform as a whole and microscopic flow is the flow through the individual fiber bundles that make up the preform. Macroscopic flow is very important in mold filling and is governed by D'Arcy's law. Extensive work has been done in this area, by way of measurement and modeling of preform permeability and mold filling. Microscopic flow is governed by surface tensions and capillary pressures and is important for obtaining good fiber wetting and fiber-matrix bonding. [3] Poor wetting and bonding lead to poor mechanical properties. Obtaining good microscopic flow is a key to the successful implementation of resin transfer molding on a commercial scale.

Cercione [3] suggested three ways to improve wetting in composite parts: spread the fiber bundles before impregnation, pre-wet the fibers to improve the wicking action, and apply the resin to the top and the bottom of the fibers. Spreading the fibers before impregnation allows the resin to penetrate deeper into the fiber bundles and applying the resin to the top and the bottom of the fibers allows more uniform penetration. If the fibers are pre-wet, less resin would be required to penetrate the fiber bundles during a liquid molding process and better wetting may be obtained.

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This paper proposes that preforms can be made from fiber tows that have been spread and pre-wet with powdered resin using an electrostatic powder fusion coating process and will lead to better part quality, such as surface finish and mechanical properties [4]. This is due to the fact that samples that were resin transfer molded with a liquid resin using powder-coated preforms would have fewer voids due to better wetting, as compared to samples that had been resin transfer molded with uncoated preforms. Hercules 12K AS-4 carbon fibers and 3M PR500 and PS500 resins were used in this research to test these hypotheses.

In the next section, the experimental procedures and tests are described. Then the experimental results are discussed. Finally, the conclusions are presented.

2. SAMPLE PREPARATION PROCEDURES

3M PR500 (liquid) and PS500 (powder) resins were used in this research because they are essentially the same resin, yet are available in liquid and powdered form. Hercules AS-4 carbon fibers (12K tow) were used as the reinforcement. The weight percentage of powdered resin on the preform was chosen as the key variable of interest. Samples were fabricated and tested for degree of fiber wet-out, as well as their densities, tangent moduli, maximum strain at failure, maximum stress at failure, and toughness. SEM photographs were taken of selected fracture surfaces to observe the fiber wetting and the locations of voids. Optical microscopy techniques were used to determine void contents and fiber volume fractions of representative samples.

2.1 Experimental Design The goal of the experiments was to determine if resin transfer molding with powder-coated preforms was possible and if it resulted in any improvement in properties. As a result, the weight percentage of powdered resin on the preform was the only process variable studied in this research. The desired fiber volume fraction was set to 50% for all samples and the 50% resin volume fraction consisted of different combinations of proportions of liquid and powdered resins. The following four levels of powder coating were used to make the towpreg: 0, 13, 23, 40 % by weight; or 0, 11, 23, and 50 % by volume.

The samples made with the 0% powder by weight on the preform were resin transfer molded with liquid resin only and the samples made with 41% powder by weight on the preform were compression molded, rather than resin transfer molded, as they contained no liquid resin. Three 15.2 x 15.2 x 0.32 cm samples were resin transfer molded at the 0, 13, and 23% powder levels and three 10.2 x 30.5 x 0.32 cm samples were compression molded with preforms containing 41% powder by weight. Fourteen layers of the towpreg fabric were used to make each sample. The production of the fabric is discussed below.

2.2 Preform Fabrication Electrostatic powder fusion coating was used to produce the flexible towpreg for weaving into the preforms. [5] Then, unidirectional, woven fabrics (plain weave) were made on a hand loom with 2.4 12K tows per cm in the weft direction and a single nylon monofilament every 1.3 cm in the warp direction. The average weight percent powder (standard deviation) on the preforms was measured to be 0, 13.3 (5.2), 20.4 (5.0), and 39.7 (4.5).

2.3 Resin Transfer Molding The RTM samples were made a the "pressure pot" setup. The resin was heated to 124°C and the empty mold preheated to 177°C. The preform was placed in the mold just before resin injection, so that the powdered resin on the preform would not cure before the liquid resin was injected. The mold was maintained at 177°C by a heated press and kept under vacuum. The resin was injected into the mold under a pressure of 68.9 kPa and was allowed to cure in the mold at 177°C for 2 hours. The extent of cure was not measured; the manufacturer's processing instructions deemed adequate to assure full cure.

2.4 Compression Molding A 10.2 x 30.5 cm cavity mold was preheated to 177°C in a vacuum hot press. The preform was placed in the mold and a load of 8900 N applied. The part was allowed to cure for 2 hours under these conditions.

After making the samples, it was obvious that these were not the optimal processing conditions. The resin wicked out along the nylon filaments and out of the samples, rather than flowing along the carbon fibers and wetting them. This led to incomplete fiber wetting and consolidation of the part, in

addition to high void contents and resin loss. The processing conditions were not optimized, due to a limited supply of towpreg fabric available for the experiment.

3. TEST PROCEDURES

Tests included fabric stiffness characterization, C-scans of the molded samples, density tests, and flexural tests. Samples were observed with a scanning electron microscope and an optical microscope to calculate the void contents and fiber volume fractions of representative samples. Details of select procedures are presented below for clarity.

3.1 Fabric Stiffness Characterization When molding complex parts, it is important that the preform be flexible, in order to closely follow mold contours. Therefore, the flexural rigidities of the towpreg fabrics were determined according to guidelines presented in ASTM D1388. The cantilever bend method was used. Test specimens for the uncoated fabric were 2.54 x 15.2 cm, but the specimens for the powder-coated fabrics were 2.54 x 30.5 cm, due to their stiffness. Each fabric specimen was tested 16 times, four times on the top and bottom of each side.

The test was also conducted for single tows removed from the fabric. The lengths of the single tows were also 30.5 cm, but the widths of the tows varied. Each tow was tested only once.

3.2 Density Test Method A of ASTM D792 was used to determine the densities of samples with dimensions of 2.54 x 12.7 cm or 2.54 x 7.6 cm (dimensions required for 3-point bending).

3.3 3-Point Bending Tests Mechanical properties, such as the maximum fiber stress at yield, strain at yield, and tangent modulus, were determined according to guidelines given in ASTM D790-90. Test Method I (3-point bending) and Procedure A were used. Properties were studied in the transverse and axial directions. Tests in the transverse direction were indicative of the fiber-matrix adhesion and provided fracture surfaces for further study of the adhesion mechanism. Mechanical properties determined from the axial tests were expected to be fiber dependent and should not depend on the amount of powder on the preform.

An Instron Universal Testing Instrument (Model TTC) was used. Three-point bending fixtures with a 5.08 or 10.2 cm span and rollers with diameters of 0.635 cm were used to support and load the sample. Three samples were tested at each of the 4 levels of powder coating. Two samples from each level were cut into specimens 2.54 cm wide and 7.62 cm long. Transverse properties were studied with these specimens and the fibers were oriented parallel to the width of the sample (and therefore, the loading nose). A length to depth ratio of 16:1 was used for these tests. The remaining sample at each level was cut into specimens which were 2.54 cm wide and 12.7 cm long. The fibers were oriented parallel to the specimen length and a length-to-depth ratio of 32:1 was used. Testing conditions were 0.051 cm/min for transverse specimens and 0.508 cm/min for axial specimens.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The volume fractions of fiber, powdered resin, and liquid resin in the finished parts ranged between 52 and 59% and are acceptably close to the desired value of 50%.

4.1 Fabric Stiffness The results for single tows removed from the fabrics are presented in Table 1. The fabrics also were tested, but the spot welds required to assure their integrity made the results suspect. In general, the tows were more flexible than the fabrics, but the flexural rigidity still increased with the powder content.

Yang, *et al.* reported the flexural rigidity of a PS500/3K AS-4 towpreg with a 50% fiber volume fraction (corresponding to the 40% powder level in this research) to be 13,500 mg-cm. [6] This value is lower than the 38,200 mg-cm measured in this research, due to the wider tow used in Yang's research (12 mm vs. 6 mm). These results lead to the conclusion that a towpreg fabric made from more widely spread tows would be more flexible and better suited for molding complex parts.

4.2 C-Scans and Visual Observations Visual observations corresponded well to the C-scan output. C-scans of samples that were resin transfer molded from uncoated preforms showed some defects on the surfaces of the samples, as well as along the nylon filaments. Visual

observations of these samples showed a few dry regions along the nylon filaments, as well as in other regions on the surfaces of the samples. C-scans of the samples that were resin transfer molded from preforms containing 13% powdered resin by weight showed defects along the nylon filaments and on the sample surfaces. The centers of these samples seemed to contain less resin than the edges, probably due to fiber movement. Visual observations showed incompletely wet-out regions along the nylon filaments and several regions of incompletely wet fibers on the top surfaces of the samples.

C-scans of the samples that were resin transfer molded from preforms containing 20% powder by weight showed the best wetting. Defects were visible along the nylon filaments, but wetting was good everywhere else. Visual observations showed very few defects along the nylon filaments and no dry fibers. However, C-scans of the compression molded samples (40% powder by weight on the preform) showed that these samples were of very poor quality. Visual observations of these compression molded samples showed defects along all of the nylon filaments and dry fibers over most of the top and bottom surfaces of the samples. This result was not unexpected, due to the non-optimal processing conditions of the compression molded samples.

Visual observations and the C-scans showed that the powder coating improved the wetting in the resin transfer molded samples, as evidenced by an apparent reduction in the number of voids and an improved surface finish. These results led to the prediction that the majority of the defects are located along the nylon filaments. Due to non-optimal processing conditions and resin loss during molding, the compression samples seemed to be generally lower in quality and may have lower mechanical properties than the resin transfer molded samples.

4.3 Density Tests The results of the density tests are presented in Table 1. In the resin transfer molded samples, the measured and theoretical densities agree within their standard deviations. However, less agreement is achieved for the compression molded samples (40% powder by weight on towpreg). The theoretical density of the compression molded samples is significantly higher (1.539) than the measured value. Resin loss during molding, visual observations, and C-scan outputs led to the conclusion that the compression molded samples were of lower quality than the resin transfer molded samples and probably contained more voids. The theoretical density assumes that there are no voids or entrapped air, which would decrease the density. Therefore, actual samples with voids would obviously have densities significantly lower than the theoretical values, as well as reduced mechanical properties.

4.4 3-Point Bending Transverse Tests The load-deflection curves were quite linear and generally showed a small amount of machine compliance at the onset of the test. The samples supported a maximum load which dropped immediately to approximately 50% of its maximum when failure occurred and then remained steady or decreased slightly with further deflection. No crushing of the samples by the loading nose was observed. Average values of the maximum stress at failure and tangent modulus for all specimens at each powder level are presented in Table 1.

The stress at failure of the resin transfer molded samples was higher than the stress at failure of the compression molded samples. This was expected, because processing difficulties, density tests, and C-scans suggested that the overall quality of the compression molded samples was lower than the quality of the resin transfer molded samples and that the void content was probably highest in the compression molded samples. However, the stress at failure did not depend on the amount of powder coating on the preform. It is still possible that a slight dependence on the amount of powder coating was present, but that it was overshadowed by the presence of voids and resin-rich areas along the nylon filaments. Even if no improvement in mechanical properties was obtained from the use of a powder-coated preform, the surface quality was improved and the mold fill time was slightly reduced. Similar results and trends were obtained for the tangent moduli and toughness, but no reduction in strain at failure was observed for the compression molded samples.

The measured tangent moduli (6.0 - 7.8 GPa) were higher than the flexural modulus of the matrix (3.47 GPa). [7] This result showed that the modulus in the transverse direction was not solely dependent on the matrix; it also depended on the fibers. This discrepancy could be caused by fiber orientations. Because the fibers were not perfectly aligned in the samples, they crossed over the fracture region and were loaded slightly. The measured values of the tangent moduli similarly were higher than the theoretical values (5.8 - 6.1 GPa).

The measured flexural strength in the transverse direction (41.3 - 62.4 MPa) was lower than the flexural strength of the matrix alone (127.3 MPa). [7] This indicated that cracks, voids or problems with fiber-matrix or nylon-matrix bonding reduced the strength. SEM photographs showed that the PR500/PS500 did not adhere well to the nylon filaments, which could have served as crack initiation sites.

Errors in the calculation of stress at failure may stem from the cross sectional area used in the calculation. The calculation was based on the apparent cross sectional area. If voids were present in the specimen, the load would be spread out over a smaller area and the actual stress at failure would be higher. In general, the transverse flexural tests showed that better properties were obtained in samples made with the resin transfer molding process. However, the amount of powder on the fabric did not have an effect on the mechanical properties in the transverse direction.

4.5 3-Point Bending Axial Tests These load versus deflection curves had long linear regions. In some cases, sample slippage or the breaking of a few fibers caused the load to drop slightly and the linear region resumed at this lower level. The failure mode was different from the transverse tests. In the axial case, short drops and level regions resembling steps occurred, rather than a sharp drop without significant further load reductions, such as those found in the axial tests. These steps indicated fiber breakage and the delamination of various layers through the thickness of the sample. Failures often initiated along a nylon filament on the surface of the sample. It was not possible to observe whether failure initiated in tension or compression. The average stress at failure and tangent modulus for each powder level are summarized in Table 1. The values of all of the properties were fairly consistent within their standard deviations and did not appear to depend on the powder content or the molding process. The properties in the axial direction were dependent more on the properties of the fibers than on the degree of fiber wetting and fiber-matrix adhesion. Therefore, little or no dependence of the properties measured in the axial direction on molding process or powder content was expected. This prediction held, but the theoretical moduli were higher than those determined experimentally. The calculation of the theoretical modulus assumes that the fibers are perfectly aligned in the axial direction and that there is no error in the fiber volume fraction. As mentioned earlier, the fibers were not perfectly aligned in the samples manufactured for this research and the fiber volume fraction varied throughout each sample, depending on the local density of the fabric.

The spread in the data stemmed from several causes, including variations in the fiber orientation. The fiber alignment varied from sample to sample, as well as across each sample, depending on the degree of fiber movement for a particular sample. This resulted in fibers that were not loaded exclusively or uniformly in the axial direction. Other causes of variation were the proximity of the loading nose to a region of high concentration of nylon filaments throughout the part thickness or variations in the fiber density of the part, because the fabric was not completely uniform.

Yang, *et al.*, reported values of flexural strength and flexural modulus for AS-4/PR500 unidirectional compression-molded composites with a 50% fiber volume fraction. [6] Similarly to the samples fabricated for this report, their samples were tested with a L:d ratio of 32:1 and they had a flexural strength of 1.654 GPa and a flexural modulus of 113.4 GPa. The flexural strength of their samples is approximately twice the strength of the samples fabricated for this research. However, the fibers in their samples were not woven or braided and therefore experienced no crimp or indentation. Fibers that have been woven or braided are not perfectly aligned along an axis, as they must pass over and under the fibers lying in the perpendicular direction. Fibers also may be broken in the weaving process, causing reductions in properties. The carbon fibers in the fabric used for this research experienced some degree of breakage and misalignment as they passed over and under the nylon filaments. Air was trapped in the indentation where the fibers passed over and under the nylon filaments, causing voids or resin-rich areas, depending on the sample. All of these factors contributed to the reduction of strength in the composite samples. The modulus of Yang's samples is only slightly higher than the modulus of the samples fabricated for this work and this difference also may be attributed to the differences between the fabric and the unidirectional lay-up.

3M reported the flexural strength of a PR500/Celion 3000 3K-8HS-Weave resin transfer molded composite with a 56-57% fiber volume fraction to be 1.083 GPa at room temperature. [7] This flexural strength is lower than the value reported by Yang, but the difference can be attributed to the difference between the 8 harness satin fabric and Yang's unidirectional lay-up. 3M's value is

intermediate to the value obtained in this research and Yang's value. This makes sense intuitively, as an 8 HS weave has fewer crimps in the fibers than does the fabric used in this research. Also, the crimps are not aligned in a single row across the width of the sample. Some added strength is obtained from the fibers oriented in the transverse direction.

4.6 Microscopy Representative SEM photographs of transverse fracture specimens are shown in Figures 1 and 2. In general, the majority of the voids were located along the nylon filaments. In samples that were resin transfer molded from uncoated preforms, some nylon filaments pulled out from the specimen and triangular gaps were observed on each side of the nylon filaments, creating voids. In the specimens molded from preforms containing 13% powder by weight, some of the gaps along the nylon filaments were filled in by resin and they were completely filled in for the samples molded from preforms containing 20% powder by weight. Photographs of the compression molded samples revealed that they had the highest void contents (none of the gaps were filled with resin).

The gaps located along the nylon filaments were caused by the tows crossing the nylon filaments. The gaps were large because the nylon filaments were much larger than the carbon fibers. The tows experienced a considerable amount of crimp when they passed over the nylon filaments.

SEM photographs of the axial test fracture surfaces showed that the specimens experienced delamination as they fractured step-wise through the thickness of the specimens. Again, smooth nylon pull-out was observed and was due to poor adhesion was obtained between the matrix resin and the nylon filaments. The wetting of the carbon fibers could be determined by the amount of "scale" on the fibers. The scaly areas were where resin had adhered to the fibers and fracture had occurred within the matrix, rather than at the fiber-matrix interface. The wetting generally improved with the amount of powder coating on the preform.

Voids and microvoids in other places besides the gaps next to the nylon filaments could be seen in the compression molded specimens. Observations showed that these samples had extremely high void contents. This result was not unexpected, as the density test and C-scan results had previously predicted that the poor-quality compression molded samples had higher void contents.

Representative fiber volume fractions and void contents calculated from the optical microscopy techniques are summarized in Table 1. Previously, the fiber volume fraction of all of the samples was calculated to be in the 52-60% range. The fiber volume fractions calculated for the 4 specimens observed in the optical microscope were slightly lower (48-53%), but they were fairly consistent from sample to sample. The void fractions were surprisingly low in the resin transfer molded specimens. The difference between the predicted value and the value calculated from the optical microscopy technique can be attributed to the variation in the amount of powdered resin on the tow, variation in the size of the preform, the range of local fiber densities, and from problems with the imaging technique. The nylon filaments were very large in comparison with the carbon fibers and appeared as large resin-rich areas in the microscope. Therefore, an image which contained a nylon filament would have a much lower fiber volume fraction than an image that did not contain a nylon filament. Due to all of the inherent variations, it is very difficult to say which fiber volume fraction is to be believed. The true value probably lies somewhere between these two.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research has shown that it is possible to resin transfer mold samples from preforms that have been pre-impregnated with a powdered form of the resin used in the liquid molding process. This combination of processes is advantageous because improved surface finishes, better fiber wetting, and reduced void contents are obtained from the combination of processes than from resin transfer molding with uncoated preforms. The samples that were resin transfer molded with preforms containing 20% powdered resin by weight had the best surface finishes and fiber wetting, the least fiber displacement, and one of the lowest void contents. Mold fill times for powder-coated preforms were slightly less than mold fill times for uncoated preforms, due to improved preform permeability or to the fact that less resin was required to fill the mold, as powdered resin was already in place. Flexural tests showed that the mechanical properties of samples that had been resin transfer molded were superior to the properties of samples that had been compression molded from powder-coated preforms, due to the non-optimal processing conditions used for manufacturing the compression molded samples.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Table 1. Experimental Results

Weight Percent Powder on Preform [%]	Surface Finish	C-scan	Density (Standard Deviation) [g/cm ³]	Trans. Stress at Failure (Standard Deviation) [MPa]	Trans. Tangent Modulus (Standard Deviation) [GPa]	Axial Stress at Failure (Standard Deviation) [MPa]	Axial Tangent Modulus (Standard Deviation) [GPa]	SEM	Void Content [%]	Flexural Rigidity of Tows Removed From Fabric [mg-cm]
0	Average	Average	1.54 (0.01)	62.4 (5.8)	7.79 (0.44)	707.1 (68.1)	96.7 (6.2)	Few filled voids	0.85 (0.73)	779.1
13	Slightly less than average	Slightly less than average	1.54 (0.01)	55.9 (7.19)	7.40 (0.60)	675.1 (8.6)	101.2 (4.4)	50% filled voids	5.16 (2.73)	7740
20	Out-standing	Best	1.53 (0.01)	62.1 (6.2)	7.78 (0.35)	739.3 (65.7)	89.9 (4.4)	100% filled voids	1.43 (0.99)	19,200
40	Very poor	Worst	1.39 (0.02)	41.4 (4.0)	5.60 (0.63)	626.8 (23.7)	92.2 (3.8)	0% filled voids	12.69 (6.97)	38,200

Figure 1. SEM Photograph, High Magnification, Transverse Test Specimen 18-5 (Compression Molded).

Figure 2. SEM Photograph, High Magnification, Transverse Test Specimen 14-2 (20% Powder by Weight on the Preform).